

Indian Creek Project, Butler County

Since construction in 2024, the nutrient benefit of the Indian Creek Project has likely been minimal. As one of the few true forested wetlands in the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, this Project could have provided unique insight if it were more connected to the watershed. However, data from monitoring beginning in August 2024 suggest no inflow from Indian Creek to the wetland occurred, and data from years preceding monitoring indicate that even in wetter years the wetland would receive only limited stream water and nutrient inputs due to its design.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 13 acres of restored wetland, consisting of three designed flow paths. Water is intended to enter via Indian Creek overflows (forest flow path, riverside flow path), as well as by adjacent field tile inflow. Water exits by surface and/or subsurface connection to Indian Creek. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as Indian Creek reaching a stage of 3.2 ft.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar forested wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Both the wetland pools and the marginally more hydrologically connected floodplain shelf were constructed at a height that severely limits inflows to this Project. Modifications to increase connectivity and lower the threshold for inflows would increase nutrient retention potential.
- Since the elevation is too high for creek flows, a limitation which could be assessed in site-selection and design of future Projects using existing datasets (elevation and USGS stream flow), researchers suggest leaning more into subsurface and surface agricultural nonpoint runoff and guiding those flows through the whole Project by capturing the main field tile sooner and directing flow through constructed flow paths.

A near complete lack of water and nutrient inputs limits the understanding that can be gained from this Project. As a result, new data collection by the Monitoring Program in 2025 will be limited to annual soil sampling.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.